

Research Article

Green-Synthesized Cobalt-Doped Magnesium Oxide Nanoparticles for Efficient Removal of Brilliant Green Dye: Adsorption Study and Process Optimization Using Response Surface Methodology

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Article History	Abstract
<p>Received: January 30, 2026 Accepted: February 23, 2026 Published: March 02, 2026</p>	<p>Cobalt-doped magnesium oxide nanoparticles (Co-MgO NPs) were synthesized via a <i>Moringa oleifera</i> leaf-extract-assisted route and evaluated for the removal of Brilliant Green (BG) dye from aqueous solutions. The adsorbent was characterized using SEM, XRD, FTIR, and EDX, confirming MgO formation with cobalt incorporation and a nanoscale morphology (≈ 82 nm from SEM). Batch adsorption experiments were conducted to examine the effects of contact time, initial BG concentration, solution pH, adsorbent dosage, and temperature. Process optimization was carried out using response surface methodology (RSM). Under the optimized conditions (contact time ≈ 100 min, $C_0 = 20$ mg/L, pH = 6, dosage = 3 g/L, and T = 303 K), a maximum BG removal efficiency of 92.1% was obtained. Equilibrium data were best described by the Freundlich model ($R^2 = 0.998$), and the pseudo-second-order kinetic model provided the best fit among the kinetic models ($R^2 = 0.9994$). Thermodynamic parameters indicated a spontaneous and exothermic adsorption process.</p> <p>Keywords: <i>Moringa oleifera</i>, Brilliant Green Dye, Co-MgO Nanoparticles, Adsorption Isotherms, Kinetics, Thermodynamics, Response Surface Methodology (RSM).</p>

1. Introduction

Freshwater availability is increasingly constrained by population growth, rapid urbanization, and expanding industrial activity. At the same time, the discharge of inadequately treated effluents continues to degrade natural water bodies, making dye-containing wastewater a persistent concern in many regions [1–3]. Industrial effluents from textile, paper, leather, printing, and dyeing operations often contain synthetic colorants and auxiliary chemicals that are resistant to conventional treatment. Even at low concentrations, dyes reduce light penetration, disrupt photosynthetic activity, and may harm aquatic life [4–6].

Brilliant Green (BG) is a cationic triphenylmethane dye widely used for textile dyeing, paper printing, and biological staining. BG is associated with toxicity and potential mutagenic effects, and its persistence in the aquatic environment raises serious health and ecological concerns [4,8]. Conventional wastewater treatment methods such as coagulation–flocculation, membrane filtration, and biological degradation can suffer from high operating costs, incomplete color removal, sludge generation, and sensitivity to operating conditions [5,7,9].

Adsorption is attractive for dye removal because it is simple to operate and can achieve high removal efficiency across a wide range of conditions. Nanostructured adsorbents are particularly promising due to their high surface area and tunable surface chemistry [6,10]. Magnesium oxide (MgO) is chemically stable and non-toxic, and it exhibits affinity toward organic pollutants. Moreover, doping MgO with transition metals such as cobalt can modify surface reactivity and defect density, potentially improving adsorption performance [2,11].

In this work, cobalt-doped MgO (Co-MgO) nanoparticles were prepared via a green, plant-assisted route using *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract as a reducing and stabilizing medium. The material was characterized using SEM, XRD, FTIR, and EDX. Batch experiments were performed to study the effects of contact time, initial dye concentration, pH, adsorbent dosage, and temperature on BG removal. Response surface methodology (RSM) was then applied to optimize the operating conditions and to evaluate interaction effects. Equilibrium, kinetic, and thermodynamic analyses were used to describe the adsorption behavior and to provide mechanistic insight.

2. Experimental Procedures

2.1 Materials

Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), cobalt nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and Brilliant Green dye were of analytical grade and used as received. Fresh *Moringa oleifera* leaves were collected locally for extract preparation. Distilled water was used for all solution preparations.

2.2 Preparation of Moringa Leaf Extract

Fresh *Moringa oleifera* leaves were washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove dust and surface impurities and then finely chopped. Approximately 20 g of leaves were added to 100 mL of distilled water and heated at 80 °C for 30 min under continuous stirring. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and filtered through Whatman filter paper to obtain a clear extract, which was used immediately as a reducing and stabilizing agent.

2.3 Green Synthesis of Cobalt-Doped Magnesium Oxide Nanoparticles

Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate (1.153 g) and cobalt nitrate hexahydrate (0.145 g) were dissolved separately in 100 mL of distilled water. The two solutions were mixed at ambient temperature, and NaOH (4 g) was added gradually under stirring (15 min) to initiate precipitation. Subsequently, 20 mL of *Moringa* leaf extract was added slowly, and the mixture was stirred at 70 °C for 3 h. The resulting paste was dried in a hot-air oven at 100 °C for 2 h and then calcined in a muffle furnace at 500 °C for 3 h to obtain Co-MgO nanoparticles. Based on the precursor ratio, the target $\text{Co}/(\text{Co} + \text{Mg})$ molar fraction was approximately 0.10.

2.4 Preparation of Brilliant Green Dye Stock Solution

A stock solution of Brilliant Green dye (1000 mg/L) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of dye in 1 L of distilled water. Working solutions (10–50 mg/L) were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution using distilled water.

2.5 Characterization of Synthesized Nanoparticles

The surface morphology of the synthesized Co-MgO nanoparticles was characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The structural and morphological properties were examined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) to determine crystallinity and phase composition, while functional groups and surface interaction were identified using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). In addition, the elemental composition was analyzed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX).

2.6 Batch Adsorption Experiments

Batch adsorption experiments were conducted to evaluate Brilliant Green removal using Co-MgO nanoparticles. A measured dose of adsorbent was added to a fixed volume of dye solution of known initial concentration and agitated at a constant speed. Aliquots were collected at predetermined time intervals, and the residual dye concentration was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer at the maximum absorbance wavelength (λ_{max}) of BG.

Removal efficiency was calculated as:

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = ((C_0 - C_t) / C_0) \times 100,$$

Where,

C_0 and C_t (mg/L) are the initial and residual dye concentrations at time t , respectively. The adsorption capacity at equilibrium (q_e , mg/g) was calculated using:

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_e)V / m,$$

Where,

C_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium concentration, V (L) is the solution volume, and m (g) is the mass of adsorbent.

Table 1. Experimental conditions investigated for BG adsorption.

S/N	Parameters	Values investigated
1	Contact time (min)	5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 80, 100, 120, 150, and 180
2	Initial dye concentration (mg/L)	10, 20, 30, 40, and 50
3	pH of aqueous solution	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10
4	Adsorbent dosage (g/L)	0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, and 3
5	Temperature (K)	303, 313, 323, 333, and 343

2.7 Adsorption Isotherms, Kinetics, and Thermodynamic Studies

Adsorption isotherms, including Langmuir, Freundlich, and Temkin isotherms, were applied to analyze the equilibrium adsorption behavior. Kinetic models such as pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order were used to evaluate the adsorption rate mechanism. Thermodynamic parameters, including Gibbs free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°), and entropy (ΔS°), were determined to assess the feasibility and nature of the adsorption process.

2.8 Response Surface Methodology (RSM)

Response surface methodology was employed to optimize the adsorption process parameters and to evaluate interaction effects on BG removal. A central composite design was used, and statistical analysis was performed to determine the optimal operating conditions for maximum Brilliant Green removal.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Characterization Studies

3.1.1 SEM Analysis

The surface morphology of the synthesized Co-MgO was examined by SEM (Figure 1). The images show rod-like and plate-like nanostructures with irregular sizes and some degree of agglomeration. From the micrographs, the characteristic particle dimension was in the nanoscale range (≈ 82 nm, estimated from SEM). Such anisotropic features are commonly observed in plant-mediated syntheses, where phytochemicals can preferentially bind to specific crystal facets and influence growth [13,14].

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of Co-MgO nanoparticles.

3.1.2 XRD Analysis

Figure 2 shows the XRD pattern of the synthesized Co-MgO nanoparticles. The diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 36.9^\circ$, 42.9° , 62.3° , and 74.7° correspond to the (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes of cubic MgO, confirming a crystalline MgO phase [15,17]. No additional crystalline phases were observed within the detection limit, suggesting that cobalt was incorporated into the MgO lattice or present in an XRD-amorphous form. The average crystallite size estimated from the Debye-Scherrer equation was approximately 137 nm; this value

should be treated as an approximation because peak broadening can also be influenced by strain and instrumental effects [18]. Differences between SEM-based particle dimensions and Scherrer crystallite sizes can arise from anisotropic morphologies, agglomeration, and the approximate nature of the Scherrer method.

Figure 2. XRD pattern of Co-MgO nanoparticles.

3.1.3 FTIR Analysis

The FTIR spectrum of the synthesized Co-MgO nanoparticles is shown in Figure 3. The broad band around 3410 cm^{-1} corresponds to O-H stretching of surface hydroxyl groups, while the band near 1645 cm^{-1} is attributed to H-O-H bending of adsorbed water.

Peaks at approximately 1458 and 1385 cm^{-1} can be assigned to carbonate species or residual nitrate from the precursor salts. The characteristic absorption in the $600\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is associated with Mg-O/Co-O lattice vibrations, supporting the formation of cobalt-doped magnesium oxide [14,15,17].

Figure 3. FTIR spectrum of Co-MgO nanoparticles.

3.1.4 EDX Analysis

EDX analysis (Figure 4) confirmed the presence of magnesium, oxygen, and cobalt in the synthesized material. The detected carbon signal is commonly associated with the carbon tape used for sample mounting or adventitious carbon on the surface. Overall, the spectrum supports cobalt incorporation in the MgO-based adsorbent [16,18].

Figure 4. EDX spectrum of Co-MgO nanoparticles.

3.2 Batch Adsorption Studies

3.2.1 Effect of Contact Time

The effect of contact time (5–180 min) on BG adsorption is shown in Figure 5. The removal efficiency increased rapidly during the initial stage and then gradually approached a plateau, indicating progressive occupation of available active sites. Approximately 69% removal was reached after about 100 min under the conditions used for the time study, and no significant improvement was observed thereafter. Therefore, a contact time of 100 min was selected for subsequent experiments and for RSM optimization [19,21,29,31].

Figure 5. Effect of contact time on BG removal (%).

3.2.2 Effect of Initial Concentration of Dye

The influence of initial BG concentration (10–50 mg/L) is shown in Figure 6. As the initial concentration increased, the percentage removal decreased ($\approx 84\%$ to $\approx 55\%$), which can be attributed to the saturation of available adsorption sites at higher solute loading. In contrast, the adsorption capacity (mg/g) increased with concentration because a higher driving force enhances mass transfer of dye molecules from the bulk solution to the adsorbent surface [32–35]. In contrast, the dye uptake (mg/g) shows a continuous increase with increasing initial concentration, as presented in the same figure. Higher concentrations provide a stronger driving force for mass transfer, enabling more dye molecules to accumulate on each gram of the adsorbent despite the reduction in percentage removal [32–35].

Figure 6. Effect of initial BG concentration on removal (%) and adsorption capacity.

3.2.3 Effect of pH

The effect of solution pH (3–10) on BG removal is presented in Figure 7. Removal was relatively lower in the acidic range (pH 3–5), which can be associated with protonation of surface functional groups and reduced electrostatic attraction toward the cationic BG molecules. Removal increased to a maximum of about 80% at pH 6, indicating this as an optimum pH under the studied conditions. At higher pH, the removal efficiency declined slightly, which may be related to competition with hydroxide ions and changes in dye speciation or surface charge [36,37]. As the pH increases, the adsorbent surface gradually becomes less protonated and eventually develops a negative charge. This enhances the electrostatic attraction between the negatively charged adsorbent surface and the cationic BG dye molecules. Consequently, the percentage removal increases sharply, reaching a maximum of about 80% at pH 6, indicating this as the optimum pH for BG dye adsorption. Beyond pH 6, the removal efficiency gradually declines, possibly due to competition from excess hydroxide ions or changes in dye solubility under alkaline conditions [36,37].

Figure 7. Effect of solution pH on BG removal (%).

3.2.4 Effect of Co-MgO Nanoparticles Dosage

The influence of adsorbent dosage (0.5–3 g/L) is shown in Figure 8. Increasing the dosage increased BG removal ($\approx 75\%$ to $\approx 87\%$) due to the larger number of available adsorption sites. The improvement became less pronounced at higher dosages, which is typically associated with site overlap/aggregation and a reduced

effective surface area per unit mass. A dosage of 3 g/L was selected as optimum for the subsequent studies and RSM optimization [36–39].

Figure 8. Effect of adsorbent dosage on BG removal (%).

3.2.5 Effect of Temperature

Figure 9 shows the effect of temperature (303–343 K) on BG adsorption. The removal efficiency decreased slightly with increasing temperature, with a maximum removal of about 92% at 303 K. This trend indicates an exothermic adsorption process, where higher temperatures weaken dye–surface interactions and favor desorption over adsorption [32,33]. Accordingly, 303 K was selected as the optimum temperature for removal.

Figure 9. Effect of temperature on BG removal (%).

3.3 Isotherm Studies

3.3.1 Langmuir Isotherm

The Langmuir model assumes monolayer adsorption on a homogeneous surface with a finite number of identical sites [32]. The linearized Langmuir equation is given by:

$$C_e/q_e = (1/(bq_m)) + (C_e/q_m) \dots (1)$$

A plot of C_e/q_e versus C_e (Figure 10) yielded a straight line ($R^2 = 0.827$). The fitted linear equation was:

$$C_e/q_e = 0.0194C_e + 0.03305 \dots (2)$$

From the slope ($1/q_m$) and intercept ($1/(bq_m)$), the Langmuir parameters q_m and b were estimated (Table 2). Using the fitted b value, the dimensionless separation factor R_l was in the range 0.033–0.145 for $C_0 = 10$ –50 mg/L ($0 < R_l < 1$), indicating favorable adsorption in the studied concentration range.

Figure 10. Langmuir isotherm plot for BG adsorption.

3.3.2 Freundlich Isotherm

The Freundlich model is an empirical isotherm that describes adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces and permits multilayer uptake [33]. Its linear form is:

$$\ln(q_e) = \ln(K_f) + (1/n) \ln(C_e) \dots (3)$$

Figure 11 shows the plot of $\ln(q_e)$ versus $\ln(C_e)$. The slope corresponds to $1/n$, and the intercept to $\ln(K_f)$. The fitted relation ($R^2 = 0.9981$) was:

$$\ln(q_e) = 1.7109 \ln(C_e) + 0.611 \dots (4)$$

The Freundlich constants obtained from the slope and intercept were $K_f = 1.84$ and $1/n \approx 1.71$ ($n \approx 0.58$) (Table 2). The relatively high $1/n$ value suggests concentration-dependent uptake and surface heterogeneity.

Figure 11. Freundlich isotherm plot for BG adsorption.

3.3.3 Temkin Isotherm

The Temkin isotherm accounts for adsorbate–adsorbent interactions and assumes that the heat of adsorption decreases linearly with surface coverage [34].

The Temkin equation can be expressed as:

$$q_e = (RT/bT) \ln(A_t) + (RT/bT) \ln(C_e) \dots (5)$$

The plot of q_e versus $\ln(C_e)$ (Figure 12) showed good linearity with $R^2 = 0.973$. Temkin parameters (A_t and bT) were calculated from the intercept and slope, respectively, and are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 12. Temkin isotherm plot for BG adsorption.

Table 2. Isotherm constants obtained for various models.

Isotherm	Constants	R ²
Langmuir	qmax (mg/g) = 51.6	0.827
	b (L/mg) = 0.589	
	RL (C ₀ = 10–50 mg/L) = 0.033–0.145	
Freundlich	Kf = 1.84	0.998
	n = 0.584	
Temkin	AT = 0.351	0.973
	bT = 39.988	

Equilibrium data were fitted to the Langmuir, Freundlich, and Temkin models using linear regression of their linearized forms. Among the tested models, the Freundlich isotherm provided the best fit (highest R²), suggesting adsorption on a heterogeneous surface with non-ideal (multilayer) uptake.

Overall, the isotherm analysis indicates that BG adsorption on Co–MgO is better described by a heterogeneous surface model than by an ideal monolayer assumption under the studied conditions.

3.4 Kinetics Studies

3.4.1 Pseudo-First-Order Kinetics

Adsorption kinetics were evaluated using pseudo-first-order (Lagergren) and pseudo-second-order models.

The linear pseudo-first-order expression is:

$$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log(q_e) - (k_1/2.303)t \dots (6)$$

A plot of $\log(q_e - q_t)$ versus t (Figure 13) showed good linearity, with $k_1 = 0.02465 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $R^2 = 0.9951$.

Figure 13. Pseudo-first-order kinetic plot for BG adsorption.

3.4.2 Pseudo-Second-Order Kinetics

The pseudo-second-order model is frequently used to describe adsorption systems where the overall rate may be governed by surface reactions and/or strong adsorbate-adsorbent interactions [35]. The linearized form is:

$$t/q_t = (1/(k_2q_e^2)) + (t/q_e) \dots (7)$$

The plot of t/q_t versus t (Figure 14) provided an excellent fit, with $R^2 = 0.9994$.

Figure 14. Pseudo-second-order kinetic plot for BG adsorption.

Table 3. Kinetics data.

Order	Equation	Rate constant	R ²
Lagergren's first order	$\log (q_e - q_t) = -0.0107t + 0.72212$	$K_1 = 0.02465 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.9951
Pseudo-second order	$t/q_t = 0.03666t + 0.06935$	$K_2 = 2.8 \text{ g mg}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.9994

Both kinetic models provided high correlation coefficients; however, the pseudo-second-order model showed a slightly better fit (higher R^2). This indicates that the adsorption rate is well represented by the PSO expression under the studied conditions, although additional transport analysis would be required for a definitive rate-controlling-step assignment.

3.5 Thermodynamic Studies

Thermodynamic parameters (ΔH° , ΔS° , and ΔG°) were estimated from temperature-dependent equilibrium data. The Van't Hoff relationship was applied using the apparent equilibrium constant $K_c = q_e/C_e$:

Where,

R is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and T is the absolute temperature (K).

$$\log(q_e/C_e) = -(\Delta H^\circ/(2.303RT)) + (\Delta S^\circ/(2.303R)) \dots (8)$$

Figure 15. Van't Hoff plot for BG adsorption on Co-MgO.

The thermodynamic parameters were obtained from the Van't Hoff plot of $\log(q_e/C_e)$ versus $1/T$ (Figure 15). The negative enthalpy change ($\Delta H^\circ = -6690.96 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$) indicates an exothermic adsorption process, while the negative entropy change ($\Delta S^\circ = -10.66 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) suggests decreased randomness at the solid-solution interface. Negative Gibbs free energy values ($\Delta G^\circ = -3.461$ to $-3.034 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) across the studied temperature range confirm that BG adsorption on Co-MgO is spontaneous under these conditions [37,38].

4. Optimization Using Response Surface Methodology (RSM)

4.1 Optimization Using Central Composite Design (CCD)

RSM was employed to optimize the operating parameters and to evaluate the combined effects of process variables on BG removal efficiency [40].

The coded levels of the four independent variables used in the CCD are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Range and levels of parameters.

Code	Name	Range and levels				
		-2	-1	0	1	2
X_1	Initial concentration, C_0 (mg/L)	10	15	20	25	30
X_2	Dosage, w (g/L)	2	2.5	3	3.5	4
X_3	pH of aqueous solution	4	5	6	7	8
X_4	Temperature, T (K)	283	293	303	313	323

In this study, four factors were considered: initial dye concentration (C_0 , X_1), adsorbent dosage (w, X_2), solution pH (X_3), and temperature (T, X_4). Table 5 lists the experimental CCD runs (contact time fixed at 100 min) and the corresponding experimental and model-predicted removal efficiencies.

A second-order polynomial model was fitted to the experimental data to correlate BG removal (%) with the coded variables. The resulting regression equation is:

$$Y = 92.1 - 2.6X_1 + 1.48X_2 + 4.43X_3 - 0.2862X_4 - 0.9008X_1X_2 - 0.30087X_1X_3 - 7.18X_1X_4 - 1.6X_2X_3 - 0.7016X_2X_4 + 6.34X_3X_4 - 1.67X_1^2 - 7.47X_2^2 - 11.95X_3^2 - 5.24X_4^2 \dots (9)$$

Table 5. Results from CCD.

Run	A: C ₀ (mg/L)	B: w (g/L)	C: pH	D: T (K)	BG removal (%)	BG removal (%)
					Experimental	Predicted
1	20	3	6	303	92.1	92.1
2	30	3	6	303	86.2	80.23
3	10	3	6	303	89.2	90.62
4	25	2.5	5	293	67.8188	69.94
5	15	3.5	5	293	67.2764	67.79
6	15	3.5	7	313	85.5201	86.39
7	15	2.5	5	313	60.3854	60.87
8	25	3.5	7	293	65.56	68.07
9	25	3.5	5	313	43.1	46.76
10	25	2.5	5	313	42.433	43.73
11	20	3	6	303	92.1	92.1
12	20	3	6	303	92.1	92.1
13	15	3.5	5	313	67.8198	67.5
14	20	4	6	303	67.9476	65.2
15	25	2.5	7	293	66.9212	68.79
16	20	2	6	303	61.0726	59.28
17	20	3	4	303	37.8087	35.42
18	20	3	6	283	73.5156	71.71
19	20	3	6	323	73.2962	70.56
20	15	2.5	7	293	59.0986	58.43
21	20	3	8	303	55.3115	53.15
22	15	2.5	7	313	86.0337	86.31
23	15	3.5	7	293	61.0538	61.31
24	25	3.5	7	313	63.1302	64.41
25	25	3.5	5	293	74.5073	75.78
26	20	3	6	303	92.1	92.1
27	20	3	6	303	92.1	92.1
28	20	3	6	303	92.1	92.1
29	15	2.5	5	293	58.0733	58.35
30	25	2.5	7	313	65.4583	67.93

The central composite design comprised 16 factorial points, 8 axial points, and 6 center points (total 30 runs). Contact time was fixed at 100 min during the optimization experiments. ANOVA results for the fitted model are presented in Table 6. In the ANOVA table, factors A–D correspond to X_1 – X_4 (A: concentration, B: dosage, C: pH, and D: temperature). The overall model was significant ($p < 0.0001$). Among the linear terms, A, B, and C were significant ($p < 0.05$), whereas the linear effect of temperature (D) was not significant within the studied range ($p = 0.6126$). The interaction terms AD and CD were significant ($p < 0.0001$), and BC was also significant ($p = 0.0287$), while AB, AC, and BD were not significant at the 95% confidence level.

The coefficient of determination for the model was $R^2 = 0.9900$, indicating that approximately 99.0% of the variation in BG removal was explained by the fitted regression. Center-point replicates showed negligible variation after rounding to one decimal place, which resulted in a near-zero pure error term in the ANOVA table. Based on the ANOVA results, all quadratic terms (A^2 , B^2 , C^2 , and D^2) were significant ($p < 0.05$). Significant interactions were observed for AD, BC, and CD, while AB, AC, and BD were not significant within the tested ranges.

Three-dimensional response surface plots (Figure 17 a–f) were generated to visualize the interaction effects between pairs of variables on BG removal. In each plot, two factors were varied while the remaining two were held at their center levels.

For reference, the main-effects (linear) portion of the fitted model can be written as:

$$Y = 92.1 - 2.6X_1 + 1.48X_2 + 4.43X_3 - 0.2862X_4 \dots (10)$$

Model adequacy was further assessed by comparing predicted and experimental removal efficiencies (Figure 16).

Table 6. ANOVA table for the quadratic model predicting BG removal (%) using CCD.

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	Remark
Model	7327.48	14	523.39	71.23	< 0.0001	Significant
A - Conc	161.89	1	161.89	22.03	0.0003	
B - Dosage	52.50	1	52.50	7.14	0.0174	
C - pH	471.42	1	471.42	64.16	< 0.0001	Significant
D - Temp	1.97	1	1.97	0.2675	0.6126	
AB	12.98	1	12.98	1.77	0.2036	
AC	1.53	1	1.53	0.2076	0.6552	
AD	825.74	1	825.74	112.38	< 0.0001	Significant
BC	43.04	1	43.04	5.86	0.0287	
BD	7.88	1	7.88	1.07	0.3169	
CD	643.21	1	643.21	87.54	< 0.0001	Significant
A ²	76.30	1	76.30	10.38	0.0057	
B ²	1528.63	1	1528.63	208.04	< 0.0001	Significant
C ²	3918.73	1	3918.73	533.32	< 0.0001	Significant
D ²	753.52	1	753.52	102.55	< 0.0001	Significant
Residual	110.22	15	7.35	-	-	-
Lack of fit	110.22	10	11.02	-	-	-
Pure error	0	5	0	-	-	-
Cor total	7437.70	29	-	-	-	-

Figure 16. Predicted versus experimental BG removal from CCD model.

The optimum operating conditions predicted by the CCD model were validated experimentally (Table 7), showing close agreement between the predicted and observed BG removal.

Table 7. Comparison between CCD-predicted optimum conditions and experimental verification.

Variable	CCD value	Experimental value
pH of aqueous solution	5.854	6
Initial dye concentration, C ₀ (mg/L)	20.708	20
Dosage, w (g/L)	2.913	3
Temperature, T (K)	302.323	303
Removal of BG dye (%)	90.417	92.1

4.2 Interaction Effects of Adsorption Variables

Figures 17(a)–17(f) present response surface plots illustrating interaction effects between pairs of variables on BG removal, with the remaining variables held at their center levels. The curved surfaces confirm the nonlinear nature of the system and the importance of quadratic and interaction terms in describing the response.

Figure 17(a). Response surface plot showing the combined effects of dosage and initial concentration on BG removal (%).

Figure 17(b). Response surface plot showing the combined effects of pH and initial concentration on BG removal (%).

Figure 17(c). Response surface plot showing the combined effects of pH and dosage on BG removal (%).

Figure 17(d). Response surface plot showing the combined effects of temperature and dosage on BG removal (%).

Figure 17(e). Response surface plot showing the combined effects of temperature and initial concentration on BG removal (%).

Figure 17(f). Response surface plot showing the combined effects of temperature and pH on BG removal (%).

5. Conclusion

Co-MgO nanoparticles were synthesized using *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract and applied as an adsorbent for Brilliant Green removal from aqueous solution. The main findings are summarized below:

- 1) SEM and XRD confirmed the formation of crystalline MgO-based nanostructures with cobalt incorporation; FTIR and EDX supported the presence of Mg-O/Co-O bonds and the expected elemental composition.
- 2) In batch experiments, BG removal increased with contact time and adsorbent dosage, and an optimum pH of ~6 was observed under the studied conditions.
- 3) Equilibrium data were best described by the Freundlich isotherm ($R^2 = 0.998$), indicating heterogeneous surface adsorption with non-ideal uptake behavior.
- 4) Kinetic data were well represented by the pseudo-second-order model ($R^2 = 0.9994$).
- 5) Thermodynamic parameters ($\Delta H^\circ < 0$ and $\Delta G^\circ < 0$) indicated a spontaneous and exothermic adsorption process.
- 6) RSM optimization (CCD) identified contact time ≈ 100 min, $C_0 = 20$ mg/L, pH = 6, dosage = 3 g/L, and T = 303 K as favorable conditions, achieving 92.1% BG removal.

Declarations

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